

Quantitative Assessment of Marine Fouling on Propeller Surfaces Using 3D point cloud analysis

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Abstract. The increase in hull surface roughness caused by marine biofouling is one of factor contributing to higher fuel consumption and carbon emissions. Marine biofouling increases drag resistance, leading to a rise in fuel consumption for ships, which significantly impacts both operational costs and environmental sustainability. However, most prior studies rely on qualitative assessments, such as visual inspection and recording, without standardized quantitative methods for evaluating hull surface roughness changes. To address this limitation, a 3D laser scanner was utilized to measure and analyze the before and after cleaning surface roughness of the twin axis propeller of the test bed vessel, Haeyang-Nuri. 3D data were collected, allowing the computation of roughness parameters, such as Ra (average roughness) and Rz (maximum profile height). These parameters were quantified across spatial regions and visualized in 3D using numerical data and color mapping techniques, providing a detailed and standardized representation of surface roughness variations This study evaluates the applicability of 3D scanning technology at the dry docking stage of test bed vessel, Haeyang-Nuri, in capturing and quantifying surface roughness changes, providing a more precise and reliable alternative to traditional qualitative methods.

Key words: Biofouling, Surface roughness, Quantitative Measurement

1. Introduction

Shipping companies are implementing various strategies in both ship design and operational management to reduce operating costs and comply with decarbonization regulations. At the design stage, efforts are made to optimize hull form to reduce hydrodynamic resistance [1], adopt alternative eco-friendly fuels [2], and install wind-assisted propulsion systems such as rotor sails [3], in order to meet environmental standards and enhance operational performance. From the perspective of operational management, ships are managed to maintain optimal speeds for economical sailing [4], and retrofitting is carried out to install exhaust gas cleaning systems such as scrubbers. In addition, alternative routes such as the Arctic Sea Route are being explored to reduce sailing distance and time [5]. Periodic cleaning of marine biofouling attached to the hull surface is also implemented to minimize the increase in surface roughness during operation.

During ship operation, marine biofouling can increase hull resistance by up to 60%, potentially resulting in a speed reduction of approximately 10%. To overcome this additional drag, increased engine power is required, leading to up to a 40% rise in fuel consumption. The elevated fuel consumption, in turn, contributes to increased emissions of CO₂ and SO₂, which have been reported to rise by 38% to 72%. [6]

Various studies to date have shown that the increase in marine biofouling on hull surfaces contributes to increased required engine power, fuel consumption, and carbon emissions. These studies have demonstrated that it is possible to determine the presence of fouling on the hull and propeller through the analysis of ship performance data. In the case of autonomous ships, it is necessary not only to identify the presence of fouling, but also to analyze the extent of fouling growth and the resulting changes in surface roughness that affect ship performance. Based on such analysis, a Ship Performance Management System (SPMS) should be developed to determine the optimal cleaning schedule from both economic and environmental perspectives. For such a system to be implemented in practice, methods for validating the reliability of predictions against the actual condition of the hull must be established. In addition, further advanced

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research is required to quantitatively evaluate the impact of fouling growth on ship performance degradation. Currently, most fouling assessments for the hull or propeller rely on qualitative methods based on the observer’s subjective judgment, such as recording the density or location of biofouling. Therefore, it is essential to develop an evaluation method that can objectively and quantitatively measure biofouling on the hull surface. This would serve as a fundamental basis for improving the accuracy of SPMS reliability verification and enhancing research on ship performance degradation caused by marine biofouling.

Meanwhile, Chapter 9 of the Maritime Autonomous Surface Ships (MASS) Code—currently under development by the International Maritime Organization (IMO) at the 109th session of the Maritime Safety Committee (MSC)—highlights the need for an efficient data management system to support ship performance and decision-making in MASS. As marine biofouling on hull surfaces significantly contributes to increased fuel consumption and carbon emissions, a monitoring and management system that determines optimal hull cleaning schedules based on changes in surface roughness is essential for economical operation and emissions reduction.

This study aims to establish a quantitative method for measuring changes in hull surface roughness caused by marine biofouling. For this purpose, three-dimensional point cloud data were acquired using a 3D scanner by measuring the hull surface of the test vessel Haeyang nuri before and after cleaning during dry-docking. Furthermore, the quantitative parameters obtained through this approach are expected to facilitate a more accurate analysis of the relationship between hull surface roughness, fuel consumption, and carbon emissions.

Table 1. Biofouling classification scale defined in the IMO guideline MEPC.378(80)

Rating	Description	Macrofouling Cover (%)
0	No fouling. Surface entirely clean. No visible biofouling on surfaces.	–
1	Microfouling. Submerged areas partially or entirely covered in microfouling. Metal and painted surface may be visible.	–
2	Light macrofouling. Presence of microfouling and multiple macrofouling patches. Fouling species cannot be wiped off by hand.	1–15%
3	Medium macrofouling. Presence of microfouling and multiple macrofouling patches.	16–40%
4	Heavy macrofouling. Large patches or submerged areas entirely covered in macrofouling.	41–100%

2. Related Work

To support the establishment of economic and environmental policies, various countries and international organizations have proposed quantitative evaluation standards for marine biofouling, aiming to objectively assess the extent of biofouling on hull surfaces.

IMO Guideline issued by the Marine Environment Protection Committee (MEPC) recommends evaluating the degree of biofouling on hull surfaces using a five-tier classification system, as illustrated in Figure 1, with the aim of minimizing the spread of invasive aquatic species. However, the classification relies on subjective judgment by the evaluator, making it difficult to consider the assessment as fully objective or quantitative.

The International Towing Tank Conference (ITTC) Recommended Procedure advises that the surface roughness of the hull and propeller be quantitatively measured prior to sea trials to ensure that it is within acceptable limits. [7] This verification helps confirm the absence of biofouling or coating damage, thereby ensuring the reliability of the speed and power performance data obtained during the trials. It is recommended that the hull surface be measured using the BMT roughness gauge and the propeller using the Propeller Roughness Measurement device. Both instruments commonly function as two-dimensional pro-

filers (2D profilometers), measuring localized sections repeatedly instead of scanning the entire surface area, and estimating the overall surface roughness of the hull and propeller based on these samples.

The method recommended by the ITTC is appropriate for evaluating surface roughness when the hull is clean, prior to the development of marine biofouling. However, it has limitations in terms of measurement range and applicability for quantitatively assessing the roughness caused by marine biofouling. Currently, in the field of hull roughness measurement, there is no standardized equipment or definition specifically designed for the quantitative evaluation of marine biofouling.

Marine biofouling tends to be heterogeneously distributed across the entire hull surface, making it essential to obtain roughness data over the full surface area rather than limited local sections. In this study, a 3D scanner is employed to acquire three-dimensional point cloud data representing the geometry of marine biofouling. Through data processing, the surface roughness caused by biofouling on the propeller is quantitatively evaluated.

Previous studies have quantitatively measured the height and volume of marine biofouling cultured on test specimens under laboratory conditions using a 3D scanner [8]. However, these studies were conducted on fixed specimens in controlled environments, and required the physical removal of organisms to distinguish between hard and soft foulers based on size. As such, the methodology is time-inefficient and not readily applicable to vessels in actual operation. In the present study, marine biofouling on an operational vessel was classified into hard and soft fouling regions based on the size of the organisms, and the surface roughness was quantified without causing physical damage.

Numerous previous studies have employed Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations to evaluate the impact of marine biofouling on hull resistance. Among them, one study classified the surface condition of marine biofouling under full-scale ship conditions into seven categories, ranging from hydraulically smooth fouling to heavy calcareous fouling, and investigated the resulting increase in hull resistance using CFD modeling. In this study, it was assumed that surface roughness was uniformly distributed over the entire hull surface for each fouling condition. [9]

However, in real marine environments, biofouling tends to be concentrated in specific areas or distributed non-uniformly, and such idealized assumptions present limitations in accurately representing actual fouling characteristics in CFD models. In this study, the propeller—one of the most geometrically complex components of the test vessel Haeyang nuri—was selected for quantitative analysis of biofouling roughness and coverage area. These results are expected to serve as input parameters for future CFD models under more realistic conditions, thereby improving the accuracy of hull resistance predictions.

3. Methodology

Figure 1. Process for roughness calculation

3.1. Selection and Calibration of the Equipment

Description	Specification
Manufacturer	CREAFORM
Model	HandySCAN 3D Silver elite
Part size range (Recommended)	0.05 ~ 4m
Accuracy	0.030 mm
Volumetric accuracy	0.020 mm +0.060 mm/m
Measurement resolution	0.030 mm
Mesh resolution	0.200 mm
Light source	14 blue laser lines

Figure 2. Specification of 3D Scanner

When selecting a 3D scanner, it is important to choose equipment that is appropriate for the size of the object to be measured and the working environment. 3D scanners are classified into contact and non-contact types. [10] While contact scanners generally offer higher measurement precision than non-contact scanners, they operate at slower speeds and are limited to smaller measurement targets, making them more suitable for laboratory environments.

The measurement target in this study was the twin-shaft propeller of the test vessel Haeyang Nuri, as shown in Figure 3, with a diameter of 0.95 meters. High-precision measurement was required to evaluate the surface roughness of marine biofouling, which ranges from the micrometer to millimeter scale.

As maintenance work had to be carried out concurrently while the test vessel was in dry-dock, the measurements needed to be completed within a limited timeframe. Considering these three constraints, a 3D scanner employing the modulated light method was selected, as shown in Figure 2, and three-dimensional point cloud data were acquired.

The 3D scanner was calibrated to compensate for physical variations caused by environmental factors such as temperature and pressure, allowing the device to return to its initial operating condition. The manufacturer's user manual provides a detailed description of this calibration procedure [11], which involves scanning a calibration plate marked with a dot matrix from multiple distances and angles to properly realign the device's internal parameters.

3.2. Measurement Target

The test vessel (Haeyang Nuri) is a 27-meter-long ship constructed from fiber-reinforced plastic (FRP), as shown in Figure 3. A silicon-based coating is applied to the hull, and the propeller is made of an aluminum-bronze casting alloy.

After undergoing hull surface cleaning during dry docking in April 2024, the vessel was operated for a period of eight months. Unlike regular commercial ships, this vessel is operated on an irregular schedule for the purpose of verifying and validating autonomous navigation technologies. As a result, it remains berthed at the pier for longer durations compared to conventional merchant vessels, thereby exposing it to conditions that are more conducive to the proliferation of marine organisms. [12]

3.3. Data pre-processing

During the dry docking of the vessel, three-dimensional point cloud data were acquired using a 3D scanner for two different surface conditions-before and after surface cleaning-as illustrated in Figure 3.

To enable roughness comparison and analysis between the two datasets, a registration procedure was required to align the scanned surfaces of the pre-cleaning propeller (Figure 3a) and the post-cleaning pro-

Figure 3. An overview of the test vessel used in this study is shown in (a), with the propeller region highlighted for analysis. Three-dimensional point cloud data of the propeller surface were acquired using a 3D scanner before cleaning (b) and after cleaning (c).

propeller (Figure 3b) into the same coordinate system. Registration was performed using the Iterative Closest Point (ICP) algorithm implemented in CloudCompare. ICP optimizes a transformation matrix by iteratively matching corresponding nearest points between two point clouds.

The accuracy of the registration was evaluated based on the Root Mean Square (RMS) error between the aligned point sets. This process minimized the alignment errors between the datasets and enabled a more accurate and reliable roughness analysis.

3.4. Handling of Missing Data during 3D Point Cloud Acquisition

Although three-dimensional scanners enable the acquisition of high-precision point cloud data, missing data occurred during propeller measurements due to two primary causes.

The first cause is attributed to physical factors. The target vessel in this study is classified as a small vessel, and the propeller to be measured has a diameter of 0.95 meters, which is smaller compared to that of general commercial vessels. However, during dry docking, the vessel is positioned at a high elevation, requiring high-altitude work and scanning in confined spaces. Under these conditions, hand tremors of the operator and sensor shadowing in narrow regions led to the occurrence of missing data.

The second cause relates to the characteristics of marine biofouling. Marine organisms exhibit complex and irregular geometries, resulting in sensor shadowing and inaccessible narrow gaps, particularly inside barnacle structures, thereby causing additional data loss.

To address these missing regions observed during the 3D data acquisition process, this study used the Hole Filling function embedded in the commercial 3D processing software VXELEMENTS (Creaform Inc.). This function automatically detects missing areas based on mesh boundary analysis and reconstructs incomplete regions through curvature-based interpolation of the adjacent surface geometry, thus achieving a smooth and continuous restoration of the scanned surfaces. [11]

3.5. Roughness Parameter Theory

Various surface roughness measurement methods have been applied to characterize the irregular geometric features of a surface. These methods can be broadly categorized into three types: statistical, fractal, and directional approaches. [13]

Among these, the statistical approach to surface roughness quantifies the geometric characteristics of a surface using a single representative value. A commonly used method involves extracting a linear profile

(“2D”) from the surface and measuring the elevation of each point relative to a reference line. The arithmetic mean of the absolute elevations, as expressed in Equation (1), is widely adopted for this purpose. This method is recommended by the ITTC for representing hull surface roughness.

$$Ra = \frac{1}{L} \int_0^L |z(x)| dx \quad (1)$$

However, biofouling exhibits locally distributed and spatially non-uniform characteristics across the hull surface. As a result, the conventional 2D linear profile-based roughness measurement method recommended by the ITTC has limitations in representing the geometric characteristics of biofouling surfaces using a single representative value. In addition, methods for quantitatively evaluating surface roughness caused by biofouling, with the aim of linking it to hydrodynamic behavior, have not yet been sufficiently investigated.

In this study, the objective was to derive roughness parameters based on three-dimensional (3D) surface profiles. In the process of 3D-based surface roughness characterization, it is essential to eliminate global trends that may obscure local surface irregularities.

The term global trend refers to the distortion of roughness characteristics caused by the inclusion of large-scale slopes or curvatures of the overall surface in the roughness data. To address this limitation, fractal-based roughness characterization methods have been considered. Among them, the roughness-length method mitigates global trends by dividing the measurement area into fixed-size windows, as illustrated in Equation (2). For each subdivided region, roughness is calculated based on the standard deviation, effectively removing the influence of global curvature from the surface data.

$$S(w) = RMS(w) = \frac{1}{n_w} \sum_{i=1}^{n_w} \sqrt{\frac{1}{m_i - 2} \sum_{j \in w_j} (z_j - \bar{z})^2} \quad (2)$$

where:

- n_w : number of windows
- m_i : number of points in the i -th window
- z_j : height of point j
- \bar{z} : mean height within window w_j

In this study, an adaptation of the roughnesslength method was applied to eliminate global trends that may arise during 3D surface-based roughness calculations. Specifically, the normal vector at each point in the 3D point cloud data was estimated using a K-nearest neighbors (KNN) algorithm, and the roughness was subsequently calculated based on these local surface normals.

3.6. Normal vector

Since the hull surface and propeller of a ship have complex three-dimensional geometries with curvature, the K-nearest neighbors (KNN) algorithm-based normal vector estimation was employed to quantify roughness parameters over these 3D surfaces.

As illustrated in Figure 4, the K-nearest neighbors (KNN) algorithm was applied to each point in the 3D point cloud data acquired using a 3D scanner. For each point, a local plane was estimated based on its 30 nearest neighboring points, and a normal vector was computed as the perpendicular direction to this plane. To implement the KNN algorithm, the `estimate_normals()` function from the Open3D library was utilized. [14] This approach enabled the removal of global curvature trends from the propeller surface.

3.7. Segmentation

To minimize distortion that may occur when calculating unified roughness parameters, the surface was segmented into hard fouling and soft fouling regions based on the size of the marine organisms.

Figure 4. Normal vector calculation based on K-NN algorithm

Figure 5. Segmentation based on biofouling scale

Hull surface roughness caused by marine biofouling exhibits a wide range of spatial scales and is characterized by a heterogeneous distribution across the entire hull surface, depending on the stage of biological growth. As shown in Figure 5, marine biofouling can be categorized into hard fouling, such as rigid organisms like barnacles, and soft fouling, which includes flexible organisms such as slime and algae. It has been reported that hard fouling has a more significant impact on hull resistance compared to soft fouling. [12]

In consideration of these characteristics, this study defined a threshold of 1 mm—based on the biological size criterion distinguishing hard and soft fouling [15]—to segment the surface area. Roughness parameters were then calculated separately for each region.

4. Result

The surfaces of the twin propellers on the test vessel were measured before and after cleaning using a 3D scanner. The acquired point cloud data were subsequently segmented into hard fouling and soft fouling regions based on the size of the marine organisms. For each region, quantitative analyses were conducted to determine the surface roughness (R_a) and the proportional surface area.

The average surface roughness (R_a) in the hard fouling regions was measured to be 2,771.8 μm on the starboard propeller and 2,648.0 μm on the port propeller. In the soft fouling regions, the corresponding R_a values were 271.2 μm and 278.5 μm , respectively.

As the vessel is equipped with a twin-shaft propulsion system employing symmetrically designed propellers, similar surface roughness characteristics were observed on both sides. In both cases, hard fouling was predominantly concentrated near the central hub area of the propeller, while the distribution of soft fouling tended to decrease toward the outer edges.

The surface coverage of hard fouling was measured to be 14.49% on the starboard propeller and 15.53% on the port propeller. According to the IMO MEPC classification system presented in Table 1, these values lie at the boundary between Level 2 (1–15%) and Level 3 (16–40%), indicating a condition where hull cleaning is considered necessary.

5. Discussion

In this study, the propeller of the test vessel Haeyang-nuri was measured before and after cleaning using a 3D scanner to acquire point cloud data, which were then compared and analyzed to quantitatively assess the changes in surface roughness and surface area caused by marine biofouling.

As a result of the quantitative analysis, the propeller surface could be segmented into hard and soft fouling regions, and their roughness was successfully quantified. Compared to the standard surface roughness of 150 μm for clean propeller surfaces recommended by the ITTC procedure [7], these findings suggest that biofouling in real operational environments can significantly impact ship performance.

Notably, instead of relying on the subjective visual grading method traditionally used to assess the extent of marine biofouling—as outlined in IMO MEPC.378(80)—this study proposed a quantitative roughness evaluation approach based on the analysis of 3D point cloud data.

This quantitative measurement approach is expected to offer high applicability in two key aspects.

First, the increase in surface roughness caused by marine biofouling leads to higher fuel consumption and elevated carbon emissions. The numerical roughness analysis method proposed in this study can serve as a useful indicator for investigating correlations between hull condition and ship operational performance. In particular, incorporating actual surface roughness data as input parameters in CFD models is expected to improve the accuracy of resistance predictions.

Second, in relation to the issue of invasive aquatic species introduced via ships—an ongoing topic of discussion at the IMO—the collection and database construction of three-dimensional digital information on hull surfaces has emerged as a critical requirement. The underwater 3D point cloud data acquired in this study provides a foundational framework for quantitatively accumulating and managing information on the distribution, density, and surface roughness of biofouling. This can be further integrated with digital twin technologies to enable continuous monitoring and data-driven biofouling management.

(a) Surface roughness distribution of the port-side propeller

(b) Segmented hard fouling region ($\geq 1,000\mu\text{m}$)

(c) Segmented soft fouling region ($< 1,000\mu\text{m}$)

Figure 6. Quantitative roughness analysis results for the port-side propeller using the proposed 3D point cloud method

Figure 7. Quantitative roughness analysis results for the stb'd-side propeller using the proposed 3D point cloud method

One limitation of this study is that surface measurements using a 3D scanner are restricted to the dry-docking period of the vessel. For ships engaged in commercial operations, dry-docking is typically accompanied by various maintenance and repair activities, which limit the available time for conducting detailed surface measurements.

To address this limitation, future research should explore roughness measurement methods based on 2D image analysis captured by underwater drones, enabling stable assessments under submerged conditions. To support such developments, it is essential to first establish a comprehensive 3D point cloud database of marine biofouling using 3D scanners.

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